

A Convenient Micro Method of Estimating Sulphur in Organic Compounds. A Modification of ter Meulen's Method.

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All micro methods of estimation of sulphur in organic compounds consist in oxidising the sulphur and estimating the resulting sulphuric acid either gravimetrically or volumetrically. The methods of oxidation of sulphur can be divided into three groups, (i) oxidation in the dry way (fusion method), (ii) oxidation in the wet way, and (iii) direct oxidation by means of pure oxygen.

Oxidation by fusion method.—Recèsei (*Chem. Ztg.* 1926, 50, 785) fused the substance with sodium carbonate and sodium peroxide and the resulting sulphate was precipitated as barium sulphate and weighed in a micro-Neubauer crucible. Emerson (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1930 50, 1291) finds that sodium peroxide is not suitable, firstly because it does not keep well and secondly, because in certain cases oxidation takes place with explosive violence. Emerson used KNO_3 in place of Na_2O_2 . The fusion mixture is prepared once for all by mixing 2 parts of Na_2CO_3 with 1 part of KNO_3 . The method is good in case of solids but not convenient for liquids, especially when they are volatile. Complete analysis requires 3-4 hours.

Oxidation in the wet way (Micro-Carius method of Emich Donau, (*Monatsh.* 112, 33, 169).—It is of limited applicability. Besides the manipulative inconveniences, it is unsuitable for organic sulphides, which are oxidised to sulphones. Electrolytic oxidation in presence of HNO_3 (method of Gasparini, modified by K. Heller, *Mikrochemie*, 1929, 7, 209) requires a special apparatus and a longer time (more than 5 hours).

Direct oxidation by means of pure oxygen.—This is the classical method of Pregl and is the most accurate method suitable for solids, liquids and gases. In this method the substance is burnt in a current of oxygen and the products of combustion are passed over red hot platinum and then over a Jena glass spiral moistened with perhydrol diluted with five times its volume of water. The sulphur is determined in the washings of the Jena glass spiral by acidifying with

hydrochloric acid and precipitating with barium chloride and weighed as barium sulphate in a micro-Neubauer crucible. In the absence of halogens and nitrogen the porcelain beads are soaked in neutral hydrogen peroxide and the resulting sulphuric acid determined volumetrically.

Later improvements of Pregl's method are concerned mainly with the complete precipitation of barium sulphate and its transference. Wintersteiner (*Mikrochemie*, 1924, 2, 14) and Eigenberger (*Z. anal. Chem.*, 1926, 68, 220) used dilute celluloid gel for rapid coagulation of barium sulphate. Heyl and Fullerton (*Chem. Zentr.*, 1923, IV, 519) used alkalimetric titration of benzidine sulphate.

Guillemet (*Bull. Soc. chim.*, 1932, 51, 1611) recommends the precipitation of sulphuric acid as benzidine sulphate and filtering through Jena sintered glass filter tubes (No. 13f. G. 3). He claims his procedure to be more rapid than Pregl's. Though these methods are excellent they require manipulative skill of the experimenter and his previous training in micro-technics. The procedure requires 3-4 hours.

Kubota and Hanai (*Bull. Chem. Soc. Japan*, 1928, 3, 168) estimated sulphur volumetrically after converting it into H_2S . The substance is heated in hydrogen and the products passed over freshly reduced nickel heated to 200° . The whole of sulphur is retained as nickel sulphide. The nickel sulphide is then taken out in a flask and heated with HCl in a current of hydrogen and the sulphur estimated exactly as in the "Evolution method" in the case of steel analysis. The method is good but requires 3-4 hours.

H. ter Meulen (*Rec. trav. chim.*, 1922, 142. *Chem. weekblad.*, 1926, 348; 1930, 19) introduced a new method of catalytic hydrogenation for the estimation of sulphur in organic compounds. The compound is gasified in a current of excess of hydrogen and the mixture is passed over a catalyst (platinised asbestos or simply pure asbestos) heated to redness by means of a Fletcher furnace. The sulphur is quantitatively converted to H_2S , which is absorbed in caustic soda. The alkali solution is then treated with acidified standard $N/20$ -iodine solution and excess of iodine titrated with $N/20$ -thiosulphate solution. Sulphur calculated from the iodine consumed: $H_2S + 2 I = 2 HI + S$. H. ter Meulen took 30 mg. of the substance and used ordinary macro-burette.

1 C. c. $N/20$ -iodine soln. Ω 0.8 mg. of S.

This method was used by the present authors for the last two years and gave excellent results.

It occurred to us that using a microburette with which 0.005 c.c. can be easily read and with $N/100$ -iodine solution we can estimate up to 0.008 mg. of sulphur. We accordingly tried to see whether by slight modification this method which is very handy and accurate requiring barely three quarters of an hour, can be applied in micro sulphur estimation.

This method has the following advantages over Pregl's method :

(1) Troublesome precipitation and transference of barium sulphate is done away with.

(2) The micro-balance is used only for weighing the original substance

(3) It does not require experience in micro-technics and infinite attention to details.

(4) It requires 1/4th the time of Pregl's method.

(5) Much simpler than that of Pregl without any appreciable loss in accuracy.

All weighings were done in a Kuhlmann micro-balance. In case of liquids Pregl's micro-technics of filling in a capillary were followed.

EXPERIMENTAL.

A diagram of the apparatus used is shown below: The apparatus consists of a quartz tube 40 cm. in length and 10 mm. in diameter. 8 Cm. of the tube length are filled with platinised asbestos which is maintained at $700-800^{\circ}$ by means of a small electric furnace 16 cm. long. The asbestos layer is kept at a distance of 5-6 cm. from the end. The end of the quartz tube is connected by means of a sound velvet cork (V) well paraffined outside, with a larger glass tube of 20 mm. in diameter and 60 mm. in length. The other end is drawn out and fitted with a ground-joint (G) with the absorption cell. The object of the wide tube is to condense the high boiling hydrocarbons which may be formed in certain cases.

FIG. 1.

The absorption cell (A) as shown in the figure consists of a glass tube of 10 mm. in diameter drawn out and fitted with a stop-cock (C)

The capacity of the cell is approximately 5 c. c. The inlet-tube which is fitted with the ground-joint (G) of the large tube goes through the side of the cell right up to the stop-cock (C). The cell is a stoppered one and just below the stopper there is a side tube (S) which serves as an outlet for the exit gas.

The hydrogen obtained from pure zinc and sulphuric acid was purified by passing successively through acid and alkaline potassium permanganate solutions and silver sulphate solution and then through a CaCl_2 tower to retain traces of the liquid mechanically carried over and partially to dry it. The gas-flow was regulated by means of a stop-cock at the rate of 1-2 bubbles per second. Rubber stoppers and joints were avoided as far as practicable. Velvet corks paraffined outside were used. 2 C c. of $N/20\text{-NaOH}$ solution were introduced into the absorption cell.

The substance was weighed in a small platinum boat and placed at a distance of 40 mm. from the furnace end. Hydrogen was then allowed to pass through the tube for 5 minutes to remove the air within the tube. A tiny micro-burner was then placed at a distance of 40 mm. from the boat and moved gradually towards the boat. After 10-15 minutes the burner was placed just below the boat and kept for 5-10 minutes. Micro-burner was then replaced by a Bunsen burner which was then slowly moved towards the platinised asbestos which had been maintained at a red heat all along. Burner was then removed and hydrogen current continued for another 15 minutes to chase the gaseous products formed.

The absorption cell was then washed out from the top with cold water (boiled air-free) into a 50 c. c. stoppered Erlenmeyer flask containing $N/100$ -iodine solution (10 c. c.) acidified with $N/5\text{-HCl}$ (2 c. c.)

The excess of iodine was titrated with $N/100$ -sodium thiosulphate solution from a micro-burette using starch as indicator. As $N/100$ -sodium thiosulphate did not keep well it was obtained by diluting $N/10$ -sodium thiosulphate solution prepared according to Watson by making the p_{H} between 9 and 9.5 by adding 3.8 g. of borax per litre of the thiosulphate solution, which was found on experience to be quite stable.

The following table gives a few results obtained with the apparatus described above.

Substance.	Wt. of the substance.	N/100-J ₂ soln. consumed.	Sulphur	
			Found.	Calc.
Thiourea	2.154 mg.	5.65 c. c.	41.96%	42.10%
Thiocarbanilide	4.200	3.65	13.90	14.05
Thiobenzamide	3.500	5.05	23.08	23.35
1 : 4-Naphthylamine sulphonic acid with $\frac{1}{2}$ H ₂ O	4.050	3.50	13.82	13.81
Sulphanilic acid with 1 H ₂ O	4.191	4.36	16.64	16.75
Amylmercaptan	9.600	18.34	30.56	30.77
Diethyl disulphide	1.825	6.02	52.79	52.46
Dipropyl disulphide	8.259	22.04	42.69	42.66

After 5 or 6 experiments the tube was burnt in a current of oxygen to regenerate the activity of the catalyst.

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